

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: DENNIE****FIRST NAME: REBEKAH****PROGRAM CODE: DCCS****COURSE CODE: ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: 1****INSTRUCTOR: DR. GULMA****Edit or delete text to show actual information below:**

The author applied US conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics

The student must use Turabian/Chicago parenthetical/in-text references (ideally with Zotero) and confirm below:

The author did use Zotero to insert references

The author did use Grammarly Premium (provided by EUCLID)

My plagiarism rate (per Grammarly Premium) is: 0%

The author used the following software: Microsoft 365 on Windows 11

List your 7 key concepts with page number in text (then bold these terms in your RP)(samples below):

1. Essay Writing (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2021, 6-12)
2. Punctuations (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2021, 15)
3. American and British English (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2021, 24-32)
4. Plagiarism (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2021, 33-39)
5. What is a Style Guide, and Why Do You Need One? (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2021, 40-42)
6. CMS Crib Sheet (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2021, 43-56)
7. Latin Abbreviations and Expressions (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2021, 58-64)

ACADEMIC WRITING COMPONENTS

1) INTRODUCTION

My initial reaction to the course material was excitement, as this is the beginning of a new chapter for learning and development. The information in period one is conditioning me for a solid foundation. During this period, I covered seven significant sections. For this response paper, I will be speaking about 1) essay writing, 2) punctuations, 3) American and British English, 4) Plagiarism, 5) What is a Style Guide and Why Do You Need One?, 6) CMS Crib Sheet and 7) Latin Abbreviations and Expressions.

2) ESSAY WRITING

Essay writing is a familiar concept in this century. As a Ph.D. student, academic essays will be crucial to my educational journey. Academic essay writing has four significant components. They are the initial essay plan, research, organizing your ideas, and creating the essay draft (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2021, 7). I understand that the initial essay plan plays a fundamental role in the essay writing process. A saying in project

management states, "Proper Planning Prevents Poor Performance." Complementary another "P" I must be mindful of when embarking on an essay is "Procrastination." Procrastination is poisonous to effectively completing an academic paper. It can lead to anxiety, which can be distraught and adversely affect creativity and critical thinking.

Hence, allocating time to adequate research is essential to fostering my academic essay-writing skills. I can use techniques such as brainstorming and mind mapping to guide the scope of my research. It is helpful to reduce the probability of reading articles that may not be relevant to the constraints of my topic. Afterward, I would organize my ideas meaningfully, enabling the essay to flow while developing my analysis. Lastly, I would formulate an article. I would incorporate essay structure and framework instructions [provided by ACA-401D period 1]. An essay structure typically consists of three major segments. They are the introduction, body, and conclusion. The concept of an introduction is that I know many trees worldwide, but I want to plant one type (from a neutral generalization to a specific niche). The introduction also highlights a roadmap (what fruit the essay hopes to bear) to the body's development. The body mainly serves as a platform to express comprehension, ideas, theories, and analysis. The conclusion summarizes the earlier information and references possible future inferences (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2021, 10).

3) PUNCTUATIONS

The icing on the cake is like punctuation in an academic essay. The details matter. The variations in punctuation and their conditional usage were an eye-opening learning experience. Also, this section expounded on the meanings behind several punctuations. They included (but were not limited to) Apostrophes, Brackets (round and squared), Semicolon colon, defining and non-defining information, dashes and hyphens, ellipsis, and the like (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2021, 16–22).

Note that if used either in place of omitted text at the end of a clause/ sentence or to indicate a pause for effect, a full-stop/comma should not follow the ellipsis. However, an exclamation mark or a question mark can and should follow the ellipsis if required (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2021, 22).

An Ellipsis (symbolized as "...") is a punctuation mark. It indicates a partial quotation of an author's text. The end text, followed by an ellipsis, suggests that only the previous text was relevant to the essay context. I like that an ellipsis allows the documentation of natural language and interaction. In daily conversations, we may pause for emphasis or to process our thoughts while speaking.

On the other hand, Apostrophes may be one of the most used punctuations. I theorize this because, on average, it has more conditions to consider when using an apostrophe than other punctuation.

4) AMERICAN AND BRITISH ENGLISH

English is one of the most spoken languages in the world. Internationally the most prominent English used is American and British English. Nevertheless, American English is more used internationally. American and British English has several similarities, yet there are distinct differentiations. Some differentiations are "Different pronunciation, although same spelling... Different spelling, although same pronunciation... Same term, Different but similar spelling and pronunciation..." (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2021, 25–26).

The differences between American and British English can become problematic when communicating if someone is unaware of a difference. In secondary school, I was allowed to speak and write interchangeably in American and British English (although not officially stated, actions implied that). An issue, however, may arise due to the ambiguity of a date. The American English date format (Month/Day/Year) is different from the British English date format (Day/Month/Year)(Cleenewerck and Gulma 2021, 31).

My homeland is St. Vincent and the Grenadines, in the Caribbean region. My country's history encompasses the Slavery era, governed by the British empire. British English has influenced my communication. Nonetheless, I do not have a preference for which English I use to communicate. I am using American English as that was the preference of EUCLID University.

5) PLAGIARISM

Integrity is not seen by someone's words but rather by their actions. A sign of integrity in academic essays is to cite others' work when using their information. A poor paper includes when someone regurgitates another's work. The reality is that not everyone practices integrity when writing and is subject to plagiarism. Plagiarism is not just copying and pasting information from other sources to create one document (without citing). It is also having a friend, family member, or acquaintance do an essay for you and stating (to your professor) that it was written by you (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2021, 34).

There are strategies to avoid plagiarism, such as in-text Citations, quotations, and paraphrasing text (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2021, 35–36). If someone still chooses to practice plagiarism, applications like Grammarly enable plagiarism assessment technology. As stated, an essay should be about creative and critical thinking, whereas plagiarism undermines that. I do not uphold plagiarism; instead, I maintain integrity in writing.

6) WHAT IS A STYLE, AND WHY WOULD I NEED ONE?

How you articulate and punctuate plays a role in your writing style. Still, a writing style reflects grammatical or vocabulary rules. It intertwines with sentence lengths, font usage, readership considerations, accepted terminology, voice preferences, and more (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2021, 41). A writing style demonstrates your writing standards. As a new student at EUCLID University, this course is essential for numerous reasons.

Two key reasons that came to mind are that EUCLID University has a level of excellence to uphold. As such, they are positioning students to develop their writing styles (while consistently guided by institutional standards). Secondly, I will likely be on a team with multi-authors in my professional career. In that case, it would be best to have established writing style guidelines for each team member. Selecting a writing style would enable consistency, clarity, and unity in collaboration. I am excited to see how my writing style progresses as I become more exposed to new concepts due to my enrollment in the DCCS program.

7) CMS CRIB SHEET

The Chicago Style (Turabian Style) writing format is for American English. American English is the recommended English variation for this course. The Chicago Style rules have guided this response paper. Some Chicago Style rules in this paper include sections heading capitalization. The page layout format is 8 ½ by 11 inches. Times New Roman font 12 usages for paragraphs. The in-text citations and references follow the Chicago Style (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2021, 50; Chicago Manual of Styles n.d.). There are other well-known writing styles for American English, which include:

- 1) American Psychological Association (APA) Style
- 2) Modern Language Association (MLA) Style

Over the years, I have used the two previously stated citations. I decided on a style to use for one reason. It was a recommended/instructed style by the previous academia I attended. Generally, I prefer to use whatever style recommendation my school suggests.

8) LATIN ABBREVIATIONS AND EXPRESSIONS

Latin abbreviation is a shortened form of a word. An abbreviation usage has its time and place. An abbreviation must be widely known and non-ambiguous to its audience to use in a text (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2021, 44). The most common Latin abbreviation in my vocabulary is "curricula vitae." In my experience of applying for jobs in different

regions of the world, 9/10 times I have seen the word "curricula vitae." I dare to say that seeing the word "curricula vitae" is expected by job searchers.

The proposed audience for writing material must be familiar with the specific language classification. An assessment of the target audience must be undergone beforehand. If not, there is a risk that readers may become disengaged while reading simply because the word choices create a barrier to understanding.

9) CONCLUSION

I like that lessons learned from this coursework can be immediately applicable. This document is the first response paper I have ever completed. It was interesting learning about how to develop an academic paper. This response paper has helped me better understand my coursework. Future response papers would be easier to draft since I have practiced using essay writing techniques.

REFERENCES

Cleenerwerck, Laurent, and Kabiru Gulma. 2021. *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1*. Fourth Edition. Bangui: EUCLID University.

Chicago Manual of Styles. n.d. "Turabian: A Manual for Writers." The University of Chicago Press. Accessed March 29, 2023. <https://www.chicagomanualofstyle.org/turabian/turabian-author-date-citation-quick-guide.html>.

Cleenerwerck, Laurent and Kabiru Abubakar Gulma. 2025. *ACA-401/ACA 401D Course Pack: Period 1*. 6th ed. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15245536>.